

Steric Control over the Threading of Pyrophosphonates with One or Two Cyanostar Macrocycles during Pseudorotaxane Formation

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Abstract: The supramolecular recognition of anions is increasingly harnessed to achieve the self-assembly of supramolecular architectures, ranging from cages and polymers to (pseudo)rotaxanes. The cyanostar (CS) macrocycle has previously been shown to form 2:1 complexes with organophosphate anions that can be turned into [3]rotaxanes by stoppering. Here we achieved steric control over the assembly of pseudorotaxanes comprising the cyanostar macrocycle and a thread that is based, for the first time, on organo-pyrophosphonates. Subtle differences in steric bulk

on the threads allowed formation of either [3]pseudorotaxanes or [2]pseudorotaxanes. We demonstrate that the threading kinetics are governed by the steric demand of the organo-pyrophosphonates and in one case, slows down to the timescale of minutes. Calculations show that the dianions are sterically offset inside the macrocycles. Our findings broaden the scope of cyanostar-anion assemblies and may have relevance for the design of molecular machines whose directionality is a result of relatively slow slipping.

Introduction

Since the first reports half a century ago,^[1–4] the field of supramolecular anion recognition^[5,6] and anion receptor chemistry^[7–13] has made significant advances. Notable applications^[14] of anion recognition include sensing,^[15–17] membrane transport,^[18,19] catalysis^[20–24] and increasingly the self-assembly of supramolecular architectures.^[25–34] Anion recognition has also been used to synthesize mechanically interlocked molecules.^[35–38] In most of these interlocked examples, anions play the role of a template, such that the anion is not part of either the thread or the macrocycle and can be removed after synthesis.^[39–42] Following one pioneering example based on a phenolate in the thread,^[43] dialkyl phosphates have been pursued as promising binding sites to furnish anion-containing rotaxanes. While this approach comes with its challenges,^[44] Flood and coworkers reported a strategy for the synthesis of [3]rotaxanes that are based on dialkyl phosphates and large anion-binding macrocycles (Figure 1A).^[45,46]

The recognition of phosphorylated molecules,^[47,48] including phosphates^[49–52] and inorganic pyrophosphate^[53–57] has been investigated extensively. By contrast, the supramolecular chemistry of organic pyrophosphates is underexplored^[48,58,59] and, to the best of our knowledge, the recognition of organic pyrophosphonates is unexplored. As dianions with tunable organic substituents, these compounds would extend the scope of anion recognition towards designer guest molecules,^[60–62] which could play a role in carbodiimide-driven chemical reaction cycles.^[63–69]

A promising candidate for the binding of such large anions is the cyanostar (CS) macrocycle (Figure 1A)^[45] that has a positively polarized central cavity in which it can bind anions

Figure 1. Overview on (A) previous work and (B) the scope of this study.

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through multiple CH hydrogen bonds. Cyanostar has been reported to bind organophosphates and organophosphonates in co-assemblies, where two (or more) macrocycles π -stack in a dimeric fashion with multiple equilibria.^[61,70–73] This relatively strong interaction has enabled supramolecular polymerization^[72] and reversible adhesion.^[62] The 1:1 binding of only one cyanostar to an anion has only been observed once for a bulky derivative (i.e., cyanosolo),^[74] but never for the parent macrocycle.

Herein, we report that control over the stoichiometry and kinetics of CS:anion binding can be achieved by modifying the steric bulk on organo-pyrophosphonate threads. A series of five pyrophosphonates was synthesized (Figure 1B) and their thermodynamics and kinetics of binding with cyanostar were studied. We found that binding can be switched between the 2:1 and the 1:1 stoichiometry, which represents the selective formation of [3]- and [2]pseudorotaxanes, respectively.

Results and Discussion

To study their interaction with the cyanostar macrocycle, we synthesized five different pyrophosphonates (PP) as *bis*-tetrabutylammonium (TBA) salts by condensation of the corresponding phosphonate with diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC). Full synthesis procedures and characterization by NMR spectroscopy (including ³¹P NMR) and high-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS) is provided in the Supporting Information. The pyrophosphonates differ in their steric bulk, ranging from the least sterically demanding homoallyl-PP 1 to benzyl-PPs with different substituents in the *ortho*-position. Substitution with –H (2), –F (3) and –Cl (4) atoms or the methyl group (–Me, 5) provides a subtle stepwise increase in steric demand. The dianionic pyrophosphonate in the center of the dumbbell-like structure can act as a binding site for the cyanostar macrocycle. The structures are depicted in Figure 1B. The cyanostar was synthesized as reported previously^[45] (Figure S45–46).

Thermodynamics of binding

To investigate complexation, we performed ¹H NMR titrations by adding the pyrophosphonate threads to the cyanostar (0.5 mM, DCM-d₂, Figure 2A). As depicted by the cartoons in Figure 2A, there are three different binding modes possible: Either a threaded 2:1 complex (green, [3]pseudorotaxane), a threaded 1:1 complex (blue, [2]pseudorotaxane) or a perched 1:1 complex (cyan), in which the cyanostar is associated with the pyrophosphonate binding site but not threaded with it. In the case of the least sterically demanding homoallyl-PP thread 1 (Figure 2B), we observed the expected formation of the characteristic peaks for the cyanostar dimer (green) that are in slow exchange on the NMR timescale as reported previously.^[70,72] Because the macrocycle dimer can arrange either as a *chiral* (') or as a *meso* isomer, two sets of diastereomeric peaks can be observed (structures shown in Figure S69). Due to its larger pseudo-stopper, addition of the

benzyl-PP 2 to cyanostar (Figure 2C) yielded the [3]pseudorotaxane (2:1 binding) only in minor amounts. Instead, we observed a new set of ¹H NMR signals (blue) that belongs to the 1:1 binding mode corresponding to a [2]pseudorotaxane. In both complexes we observed a strong downfield shift for protons H_a and H_d that point inside the binding cavity and is consistent with CH hydrogen bonding to the pyrophosphonate anions. Interestingly, the [3]pseudorotaxane displays shifts in H_a and H_d that more closely resemble the shifts seen upon complexation of dianions^[70] rather than monoanions.^[45] The minor shift seen for protons H_b and H_c are consistent with their locations on the outside of the macrocycles. Likewise, we exclusively observed the formation of [2]pseudorotaxane when performing the analogous titration with F-benzyl-PP 3 (Figure 2D), where the steric demand is further increased. Binding also leads to a new set of signals for the pyrophosphonates phenyl protons (grey, shifted upfield under the influence of cyanostar's π -system). When increasing the equivalents of the pyrophosphonate up to 50, we could observe that the equilibrium is shifted towards the [2]pseudorotaxane even in the case of homoallyl-PP 1 (Figure S64 and Figure S70), because the cyanostar availability is decreased.

For all investigated threads, the signals of the unthreaded cyanostar (cyan) broaden upon addition of excess pyrophosphonate as a result of forming a perched complex that is in fast exchange with the free cyanostar on the NMR timescale. The sharp signals for both the 2:1 and the 1:1 pseudorotaxanes indicate slow exchange on the NMR timescale. For the two most sterically demanding pyrophosphonates 4 and 5 (–Cl, –Me), no evidence of threading was observed. Even at increased temperatures up to 403 K (VT NMR, Figure S67), ¹H NMR spectroscopy did not indicate any rotaxane formation in C₂D₂Cl₄ (upon cooling to ambient temperature), from which we conclude that even the Cl-substituted stopper is already too large to allow slipping of cyanostar. Further fine-tuning of the stoppers (e.g., five-membered rings) could potentially facilitate a convenient synthesis of cyanostar rotaxanes by a slipping approach (heating followed by cooling).^[75,76]

To complete the characterization of the complexes, we measured high resolution mass spectra (HRMS) of the pseudorotaxanes and found corresponding signals to be in good agreement with the calculated isotopic patterns (Figures S74–75). When applying a collision voltage to the pseudorotaxane in the gas-phase, the signal decreased in favor of the free pyrophosphonates indicating dethreading (Figure S76). The binding of the cyanostar to the pyrophosphonates in solution was further corroborated by ¹H–¹H NOE NMR spectroscopy, where a cross-peak between the inner protons of the cyanostar (H_a and H_d) and the benzyl protons of the pyrophosphonate was observed (Figure S73).

The binding was investigated further by ³¹P NMR spectroscopy. In a titration experiment, we added cyanostar to benzyl-PP 2 and F-benzyl-PP 3 (2.5 mM, DCM-d₂ or CDCl₃) and monitored the decreasing peak of the free pyrophosphonate and the increasing peak of [2]pseudorotaxanes. As the species are in slow exchange, we were able to integrate the two peaks

Figure 2. ^1H NMR titrations. (A) Schematic illustration of experiments leading to either $[n]$ pseudorotaxanes ($n = 2, 3$) or the perched complex. (B) Titration of homoallyl-PP **1** into a solution of CS leads to the formation of [3]pseudorotaxane (2:1 complex). (C) Titration of benzyl-PP **2** to CS leads to a mixture of 1:1 and 2:1 complexes. (D) Titration of F-benzyl-PP **3** to CS leads exclusively to the formation of [2]pseudorotaxane (1:1 complex). The corresponding signals are color-coded as follows: free and perched CS generate a single fast-exchange signature colored cyan, the 2:1 complex is green, and the 1:1 complex is blue, while the phenyl-protons (free and bound) are grey. ^1H NMR titrations (600 MHz) were performed with 0.5 mM CS, at 298 K in DCM-d_2 .

and determine binding constants by applying the mass action law (Figures S77–S80). All binding constants are moderate and on the order of 10^3 M^{-1} (see Table 1). Unfavorable steric interactions could account for the weaker binding compared to previously studied anions.^[45,74]

Kinetics of binding

We also explored the kinetics of threading cyanostar macrocycles onto the pyrophosphonates. As illustrated in Figure 3A, we added the pyrophosphonates (2 mM) to a solution of cyanostar in DCM-d_2 (1 mM) and monitored the formation of the corresponding pseudorotaxanes by ^1H NMR spectroscopy. For homoallyl-PP **1** (Figure S58) and benzyl-PP **2** (Figure 3B and

Table 1. Summary of binding thermodynamics and kinetics of the [2]pseudorotaxanes. ^[87,88]			
Pyrophosphonate	A value ^[a]	K_A [M^{-1}] ^[b]	t_{50} ^[c]
1 (homoallyl)	n.a.	n.d.	< 20 s
2 (benzyl)	H: 0.0	2600 ± 300 (CDCl_3)	< 20 s
3 (F-benzyl)	F: 0.15	1300 ± 300 (CDCl_3) 4400 ± 500 (CD_2Cl_2)	~3.5 min
4 (Cl-benzyl)	Cl: 0.43	No threading ^[d]	
5 (Me-benzyl)	Me: 1.70	No threading ^[d]	

[a] Indicates the size of the *ortho*-substituent on the phenyl group.^[89,90] [b] At 298 K, 2.5 mM. Only CDCl_3 was used for benzyl-PP **2** where no 2:1 binding was observed due to the lower polarity of this solvent (compared to CD_2Cl_2). [c] At 298 K, 1 mM in CD_2Cl_2 . [d] Up to 333 K in CDCl_3 or up to 403 K in $\text{C}_2\text{D}_2\text{Cl}_4$ (S52). n.a.: not applicable. n.d.: not determined (complex mixture).

Figure 3. Binding kinetics. (A) Illustration of the experiment: The threading kinetics of cyanostar on the pyrophosphonates is monitored. (B) Formation of the [2]pseudorotaxane (1:1 binding) over time (as indicated by the integral of the characteristic H_d proton) with pyrophosphonates **2** and **3**, respectively. All kinetic experiments were performed at 298 K, 1 mM in $CDCl_3$.

S59) the threading is too fast to be observed in these experiments. Taking the delay between addition of the pyrophosphonate and the first measurement into account, the time until 50% of the final equilibrium is reached (t_{50}) is therefore below 20 s. When we studied the de-threading kinetics of the 1:1 complex between cyanostar and benzyl-PP **2**, we found that it made a difference whether we initiated de-threading by addition of PF_6^- (relatively slow de-threading with $t_{50} \approx 120$ s; Figure S61) or water (fast de-threading with $t_{50} < 20$ s, Figure S62). The steric demand of F-benzyl-PP **3** (Figure 3B and Figure S60) slowed down the threading significantly and we determined $t_{50} \approx 3.5$ min. Equilibrium is reached after approximately 15 min (Figures S48–49), so this compound can be considered a borderline case between pseudorotaxane and rotaxane.^[77] Such relatively slow threading kinetics could be interesting for the design of directional molecular machines,^[78–82] in which a ratcheting step relies on a molecular “valve”.^[83–86]

Variable temperature (VT) NMR spectroscopy was performed (Figures S50–S53) to gain insights into the kinetics associated with formation of the perched interaction from the free cyanostar. As mentioned above, formation of this perched structure is fast on the NMR time scale at 298 K. Decreasing the temperature to 233 K slows down this process significantly, as indicated by peak splitting of the cyanostar signals into those that can be assigned to the free and perched structures (Figure S65). At 333 K, on the other hand, sharp peaks are observed for free cyanostar indicating fast kinetics (in $CDCl_3$).

The results of both the thermodynamic and the kinetic studies are summarized in Table 1. We found that increasing the steric bulk of the pyrophosphonates - as indicated here by the A values^[89–91] - decreases the threading kinetics over (at least) one order of magnitude. The binding thermodynamics (2:1 vs. 1:1 vs. no binding) is strongly dependent on the size of the pseudo-stoppers, with the K_A value of the more sterically

demanding F-benzyl-PP **3** being slightly lower than benzyl-PP **2** (in $CDCl_3$).

Molecular modeling

In order to investigate how the steric demand of the pyrophosphonate dianions contribute to differences in the 1:1 and 2:1 binding modes, we performed density functional theory (DFT) calculations on the [3]pseudorotaxane with homoallyl-PP **1** and the [2]pseudorotaxane with F-benzyl-PP **3** (RB3LYP/6-31G(D), gas phase). Optimized geometries (Figure 4) were generated with the TBA^+ cation but it was omitted in parts of the figure for the purpose of clarity (see Figures S81–85). Consistent with reported (pseudo)rotaxanes formed between phosphate threads and cyanostar,^[45,46,61] both structures show C–H...O hydrogen bonds between the polar cyanostar CH donors and the oxygen atoms on the pyrophosphonate threads. The [2]pseudorotaxane with F-benzyl-PP **3** shows an average hydrogen bond distance of 2.4 Å while the [3]pseudorotaxane with homoallyl PP **1** has an average hydrogen bond distance of 2.5 Å. In the case of the [3]pseudorotaxane with homoallyl PP **1**, we also observe a very short interaction ($d_{H...O} = 2.1$ Å) between α -proton of one TBA^+ cation and an oxygen from the pyrophosphonate (Figure S83). This contact is consistent with reported crystal data of cyanostar and TBA -bisulfate^[92] or TBA -organophosphate^[70] complexes.

Interestingly, we observe that the π -stacked cyanostar dimer is not centered on the homoallyl PP **1** thread but shifted non-symmetrically to one side. To investigate the origin of this off-center position, we modelled binding of the simplest dianionic pyrophosphonate, $H_2P_2O_5^{2-}$, with the cyanostar dimer (Figure S84). Here we also observe the non-symmetric binding

Figure 4. Equilibrium geometries of (A) the [3]pseudorotaxane comprised of two CS macrocycles and homoallyl-PP **1** and (B) the [2]pseudorotaxane comprised of one CS and F-benzyl-PP **3** shown as stick (left) and space-filling models (right). Equilibrium geometries were optimized using density functional theory (RB3LYP/6-31G(D)). Hydrogen atoms and TBA counter ions are omitted from the images on the left for clarity. Color code: C (grey), N (blue), O (red), F (green), P (orange).

mode even without substituents, indicating the steric profile of pyrophosphonate itself does not allow centralization inside the cyanostar dimer. This steric outcome naturally leads to a more limited stabilization of the dianionic pyrophosphonate by the cyanostar(s) with the available external oxygen atom shown to form the short contact with the TBA⁺ cation. When the steric profile of the anionic thread becomes even more demanding, as with F-benzyl-PP **3** (Figure 4B and Figure S85), only one cyanostar can bind to the pyrophosphonate. This preference for one macrocycle emerges from the combination of the pyrophosphonate's steric profile and the steric proximity of the fluorophenyl.

Conclusions

We report the first example of organo-pyrophosphonate recognition and characterize their threading inside cyanostar macrocycles, which is modulated by the size of the organic substituent to afford pseudorotaxanes with one or two macrocycles (Figure 5). We synthesized a series of five short threads, explored their non-covalent C–H...O hydrogen bonding interactions with the anion-binding cyanostar macrocycle and characterized both thermodynamics and kinetics of threading. Using NMR titrations, we found that the previously reported propensity for cyanostar to form 2:1 complexes can be switched off completely by fine-tuning the steric profile of the pyrophosphonate. While DFT shows the pyrophosphonate anion is unable to perfectly fit inside two macrocycles, experiments show the homoallyl-PP alone can form a [3]pseudorotaxane. Increasing the steric demand yielded the successful assembly of a [2]pseudorotaxane with the F-benzyl-PP pyrophosphonate in chlorinated solvents. This first example of a 1:1 CS:anion complex was further corroborated by HRMS and NOESY NMR. We therefore demonstrate an approach to make use of substituents in designer anions with different steric demand to tune supramolecular recognition. Furthermore, we

gained steric control not only over the thermodynamic binding mode, but also over the threading kinetics, which vary over at least one order of magnitude. Threading kinetics on the minutes-to-hours timescale represent the boundary between pseudorotaxanes and rotaxanes^[77] and can be harnessed to create directional molecular machines, which will be at the focus of future work.

Experimental Section

Synthesis of pyrophosphonates (PP): Tetrabutylammonium phosphonates were dissolved in DCM and 10 equivalents of *N,N'*-diisopropylcarbodiimide (DIC) were added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 48 h. DCM was evaporated and the residue was purified by reversed-phase column chromatography. Lyophilization yielded the desired pyrophosphonates in 29–46%.

¹H NMR titrations: All compounds were dried for 24 h under oil pump vacuum before use. A 0.5 mM solution of cyanostar in DCM-d₂ (dried over 3 Å molecular sieves) was prepared. A freshly prepared stock solution of the corresponding pyrophosphonate (25 mM, DCM-d₂) was added in a stepwise titration (1 μL = 0.1 equiv). The solutions were equilibrated according to their binding kinetics (see below) before measurement. All measurements were performed on a Bruker Avance 600 NEO spectrometer (600 MHz).

High Resolution Mass Spectrometry Electrospray Ionization (HRMS-ESI): A 200 μM solution of a 1:1 mixture of cyanostar and the pyrophosphonate in HPLC-grade DCM was prepared and HRMS was measured with ESI in the negative ion mode on an Agilent 1260 Infinity II system with a 6546 LC/QTOF mass spectrometer. In the 2D-MS experiment a collision voltage of 10–30 V was applied to the [2]pseudorotaxane in the gas phase.

³¹P NMR titrations and determination of binding constants (*K_A*): 500 μL of a 2.5 mM solution of the corresponding pyrophosphonate was prepared in CDCl₃ or DCM-d₂. A 50 mM solution of cyanostar in CDCl₃ or DCM-d₂ was added in a stepwise titration (5 μL = 0.2 equiv. cyanostar). ³¹P NMR was measured and the ratio of free pyrophosphonate and [2]pseudorotaxane was obtained by relative integration. Concentrations (including cyanostar) were calculated

Figure 5. Overview of key findings of this study. Five different pyrophosphonates divided into three categories by their steric bulk.

considering the total volume. Binding constants (K_A) were determined (as a mean value of seven measurements with the standard deviation as error) under the reasonable assumption that exchange is slow on the NMR time scale [Eq. (1)]:

$$K_A = \frac{[HG]}{[G] \times [H]} = \frac{[\text{pseudorotaxane}]}{[\text{pyrophosphonate}] \times [CS]} \quad (1)$$

Binding kinetics by ^1H NMR monitoring: 25 μL of a cyanostar stock solution (20 mM in DCM-d_2) was diluted with 435 μL DCM-d_2 , 40 μL of a stock solution (25 mM in DCM-d_2) of the corresponding pyrophosphonate (PP) were added (1 mM CS + 2 mM PP) and a series of NMR spectra were recorded. A lag time of 120 s between addition of pyrophosphonate and the first measurement was taken into account. A characteristic peak for the formation of the [n]pseudorotaxane was monitored over time.

Variable temperature (VT) NMR studies: 25 μL of a 20 mM cyanostar stock solution (in CDCl_3) and 40 μL of a 25 mM stock solution of the corresponding pyrophosphonate (in CDCl_3) were diluted to 500 μL with CDCl_3 (1 mM CS + 2 mM PP). VT ^1H NMR was measured starting from the lower temperature. The temperature was equilibrated for 5 min before each measurement.

DFT calculations: A restricted hybrid HF-DFT SCF calculation was performed using Pulay DIIS + geometric direct minimization SPARTAN'20 on the RB3LYP functional with a 6–31G(D) basis set for the geometry optimization.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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